

Synthesis of Novel Pyrazoline Derivatives. I. Reaction of *erythro*-2,3-Dibromoketones with Semi- and Thiosemicarbazides

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Manuscript received 23 June 1994, revised 1 August 1995, accepted 9 October 1995

The reaction of a series of *erythro*-2,3-dibromo-1,3-diaryl-1-propanones with four molar equivalents of semicarbazide hydrochloride or thiosemicarbazide in dioxane or ethanol leads to the formation of trisubstituted pyrazolines and their 4-bromo derivatives. The pyrazolines have been identified by chemical and spectral data. A reaction mechanism is also proposed.

The reaction of 2,3-dihaloketones with different nucleophiles is reported to afford a variety of heterocyclic compounds. The reaction of 2,3-dibromo-1,3-diaryl-1-propanones with hydroxylamine hydrochloride¹ has been found to give isoxazole derivatives, while reactions of these dibromoketones with hydrazine² and phenylhydrazine³ produce pyrazoline and 4-bromopyrazoline derivatives respectively. The reactions of 2,3-dibromo-1,3-diaryl-1-propanones with ammonia and primary amines give the corresponding aziridine derivatives^{4,5}, whereas 1,3-diazobicyclohex-3-enes are formed when these dibromoketones are treated with methanolic ammonia and then with formaldehyde or acetone. Furthermore, aurone derivatives were obtained from amine-catalysed cyclisation of 2,3-dibromoketones⁵.

The reaction of a series of *erythro*-2,3-dibromo-1,3-diaryl-1-propanones with semicarbazide hydrochloride and thiosemicarbazide has received a little attention. This prompted us to carry further investigation of this reaction and suggest a possible mechanism.

Results and Discussion

erythro-2,3-Dibromo-1,3-diaryl-1-propanones (**1a-e**) were prepared by bromination of *trans*-1,3-diaryl-2-propanones (**2a-i**). The configuration of the dibromoketones **1a-i** was determined from their ¹H nmr spectra as an *erythro*-form ($J_{2,3}$ 9.8–12.0)⁷.

Reductive debromination products (**2a-g**) were observed when *erythro*-2,3-dibromoketones (**1a-g**) were reacted with semicarbazide hydrochloride in 1 : 2 molar ratio, whereas **2a-i** were formed in case of the reaction of **1a-i** with thiosemicarbazide under similar condition. The dehydrobromination products (**3h,i**) were isolated from the reaction of the corresponding *erythro*-2,3-dibromo-3-(*p*-halophenyl)-1-phenyl-1-propanones (**1h,i**) with semicarbazide hydrochloride under the same condition. Using 1 : 4 molar ratio, the corresponding 3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazoline-1-carboxamides (**4a-g**) and 3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazoline-1-thiocarboxamides (**5a-i**) were isolated from these reactions with semicarbazide hydrochloride or thiosemicarbazide respectively. In the case of the reaction of **1h,i** with semicarbazide hydrochloride, the corresponding 4-bromo-5-(*p*-

halophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-pyrazoline-1-carboxamides (**6h,i**) were obtained.

Ir spectra of **4a-g** and **6h,i** showed three main bands at 3 417–3 494 (NH of carboxamide moiety), 1 643–1 690 (C=O) and 1 585–1 661 cm⁻¹ (C=N), beside characteristic bands for C–Br in case of **6h** and **6i** at 565 and 563 cm⁻¹ respectively. Their thio analogues (**5a-i**) revealed bands at 3 407–3 419 (NH), 1 585–1 603 (C=N) and 1 244–1 279 cm⁻¹ (C=S). The electronic spectra showed characteristic maxima for π - π^* corresponding to the conjugated aromatic rings in the 2-pyrazoline derivatives in the range 215–296 and 326–360 nm for **4a-g** and **5a-i** respectively; another maxima at 205–222 and 196–294 nm corresponds to n - π^* transition for carbonyl chromophore of the carboxamide and thiocarboxamide residues respectively⁹.

¹³C nmr spectra for **4a**, **4f** and **6h** showed signals at δ 42.330–46.109 (C-4), 49.515–59.740 (C-5), 113.860–128.698 (C-3), 126.390–154.940 (Ar.C-atoms) and 192.00–202.00 ppm (C,C=O). For compound **4f** a characteristic signal at δ 55.070 ppm (C, –OCH₃) was observed.

¹H nmr spectra for the 2-pyrazoline derivatives (**4a-g**, **5a-i**) were characterised by the appearance of ABX system¹⁰ due to *geminal-vicinal* coupling between 4-CH₂ and 5-CH protons. Thus, the 5-CH proton appeared as a doublet of doublet at δ 3.65–5.75, while the 4-CH₂ protons appeared as two doublets of doublet at δ 2.25–4.00 and 1.00–3.35. The ¹H nmr spectra of 4-bromo-2-pyrazoline derivatives (**6h,i**) showed different patterns from those obtained for the above 2-pyrazoline derivatives. The pyrazoline protons (4-CH and 5-CH) appeared as two resolved doublets (AB system) centered at δ 6.75, 5.80 and 6.65, 5.80 for **6h** and **6i** respectively. The two *vicinal*-protons (4-CH and 5-CH) are located anti to each other (J 13 Hz)³. A good chemical evidence for the configurational assignment at C-4 and C-5 of the 4-bromo-2-pyrazoline ring was established on the basis of the difficulty for the elimination of HBr molecule with triethanolamine, and this means a *syn*-configuration for C–Br and C–H. Mild oxidation of the pyrazolines (**4a-g**) and their thio analogues (**5a-i**) by bromine water⁵ led to the formation of the corresponding pyrazoles. Thus, oxidation of **4a**, **4c**, **4f** and **5g** gave the

Scheme 1

Pyrazoles 7a, 7c, 7f and 8g respectively (Scheme 1).

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTIC MASS SPECTRAL PEAKS OF 4-BROMOPYRAZOLES (6h,i)

Compd. no.	(M ⁺) m/z	100	Mass assignments
6h	379	7.5	
	380	2.5	
	381	5.0	
	241	19.5	
	243	7.2	$[M-NCONH_2]^+ + H_2 - HBr$
6i	111	8.3	
	113	3.0	
	423	1.5	
	425	3.0	
	366	3.0	
	368	6.2	
	155	18.8	$M-NCONH_2]^+$
157	18.7		

The ir spectra indicated the appearance of new stretching C=C band at 1595–1600 cm⁻¹ reflecting the formation of endocyclic double bond. The disappearance of the ABX system for the ¹H nmr spectra of pyrazolines 4a, 4c, 4f and 5g was an indication that oxidation must have occurred. Further evidence concerning the structure of 4-bromopyrazolines 6h,i was derived from their mass spectral data (Table 1).

Mechanism of reactions : The reaction of the dibromoketones (1a-i) with semicarbazide hydrochloride depends on the electronic nature of the substituents (X). Firstly, debromination takes place to give the corresponding α,β -unsaturated ketones (2a-g) except for the reaction of 1h,i which involves a debromination affording the corresponding α -bromovinylketones 3h,i as intermediates. This may be attributed to the strong inductive effect of the halogen atom. In case of the reaction of 1g (X=NO₂), debromination proceeds to give the corresponding α,β -unsaturated ketone (2g) via the formation of the carbanion (9g) which is facilitated by the relative strong stabilising effect of the nitro group over the halogen atoms (Cl, Br). In the second step, intermediates 2a-g, 3h,i are attacked by another molecule of semicarbazide hydrochloride affording the corresponding pyrazolines 4a-i, 6h,i via the formation of the semicarbazone derivatives followed by cyclisation. On the other hand, the reaction of 1a-i with thiosemicarbazide, is independent of the nature of the substituents (X), i.e. debromination takes place in all the systems studied to give the corresponding α,β -unsaturated ketones (2a-i) as intermediates. This contradiction may be attributed to the

relative high nucleophilicity of thiosemicarbazide over semicarbazide hydrochloride. Similarly, the second molecule of thiosemicarbazide attacks the intermediates **2a-i** leading to the corresponding pyrazolines **5a-i** via the formation of thiosemicarbazone derivatives (Scheme 1).

One of these thiosemicarbazone derivatives (**10h**) could be synthesised by refluxing the corresponding dibromoketone (**1h**) with thiosemicarbazide under similar conditions for about 6 h (which is half the allowed time for interaction). Compound **10h** could be converted to the corresponding pyrazoline **5h** by refluxing for a longer time in ethanol.

It is noteworthy, to mention that we have also synthesised all of these pyrazoline derivatives (**4a-g**, **5a-i**, **6h,i**) by the reaction of the corresponding α,β -unsaturated ketones (**2a-i**) or α -bromovinylketones (**3h,i**) with two molar equivalents of the appropriate semicarbazides under similar reaction conditions.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Kofler block and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 4B and Unicam SpUV spectrophotometers, ^1H nmr spectra on a Varian XL-300 (300 MHz) and Varian EM-390 (90 Hz) spectrometers using TMS as internal standard, ^{13}C nmr on a Varian XL-300 spectrometer (75 MHz) at Northeastern University, Boston, U.S.A. using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a MS-5988 instrument at Microanalytical Centre at Cairo University. Microanalyses were done at Cairo University and at National Research Center, Cairo-Dokki, Egypt.

erythro-2,3-Dibromo-1,3-diaryl-1-propanones (1a-i) : These were prepared by the bromination of *trans*-1,3-diaryl-2-propanones (**2a-i**) in chloroform as reported previously^{7,11}.

3,5-Diaryl-2-pyrazoline-1-carboxamides (4a-g) : A solution of the appropriate dibromoketone (**1a-g**; 0.01 mol) in dioxane (10 ml) and semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.04 mol) in acetic acid-water mixture (10 ml; 1 : 3, v/v) was refluxed for 10–30 h depending on the substrate used. The solvent was then evaporated and the residue was poured into ice-cold water. The separated solid (yields > 75%) were washed with water, dried and crystallised from the appropriate solvent : **4a**, m.p. 192° (Found : C, 72.30; H, 5.20; N, 15.80. Calcd. for : C, 72.45; H, 5.70; N, 15.84%); ν_{max} 3 491 (NH), 1 685 (C=O), 1 661 cm^{-1} (C=N); λ_{max} (e) 294 (45 300), 205 nm (10 200); δ 7.35, 7.80 (m, ArH), 5.40 (d/d, 5-CH), 3.75, 3.20 (2d/d, 4-CH₂), 6.55 (s, CONH₂); **4b**, 184°, **c**, 176°, **d**, 174°, **f**, 221°, **g**, 294°.

4-Bromo-5-p-halophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-pyrazoline-1-carboxamides (6h,i) : These were prepared by using the previous method with 2,3-dibromo-3-(*p*-halophenyl)-1-phenyl-1-propanones (**1h,i**) as substrate : **6h**, m.p. 192°; ν_{max} 3 435 (NH), 1 677 (C=O), 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=N); λ_{max} (e) 296 (14 771), 253 (17 820), 205 nm (20 100); δ 7.00–8.00 (m, ArH), 5.80 (d, 5-CH), 6.75 (d, $J_{4,5}$ 13 Hz, 4-CH), 7.80 (s, CONH₂); **6i**, 144°.

3,5-Diaryl-2-pyrazoline-1-thiocarboxamides (5a-i) : A mixture of the appropriate dibromoketone (**1a-i**) (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) and thiosemicarbazide (0.04 mol) in presence of glacial acetic acid (few drops) was refluxed for 12–14 h. The solvent was then removed and the separated solid were washed with water, dried and crystallised from the appropriate solvent : **5a**, m.p. 56°; ν_{max} 3407 (NH), 1 589 (C=N), 1 244 cm^{-1} (C=S); λ_{max} (e) 326 (1 098), 196 nm (1 533); δ 6.65–7.90 (m, ArH), 4.90 (d/d, 5-CH) 3.20, 1.00 (2d/d, 4-CH₂), 10.00 (s, CSNH₂); **5b**, 84°, **c**, 139°, **d**, 146°, **f**, 91°, **g**, 144°, **h**, 94°, **i**, 124°.

3,5-Diarylpyrazole-1-carboxamides (7a,c,f) and 5-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-3-phenylpyrazole-1-thiocarboxamide (8g) : A 5% bromine water (15 ml) was gradually added to a suspension of the appropriate pyrazoline (**4a,c,f**, **5g**, 0.003 mol) in water (10 ml) while stirring. The reaction mixture was then left overnight at room temperature and the separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from methanol : **7a**, m.p. 165°; ν_{max} 3 389 (NH), 1 675 (C=O), 1 662 (C=N), 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=C), λ_{max} (e) 258 (16 595), 206 nm (20 417); δ 7.45–7.60 (m, ArH, 4-CH), 6.55 (s, CONH₂); **7c**, 136°, **f**, 122°; **8g**, 119°; ν_{max} 3 494 (NH), 1 279 (C=S), 1 646 (C=N) 1 595 cm^{-1} (C=C); λ_{max} (e) 286 (56 200), 206 nm (84 330); δ 7.00–8.10 (m, ArH, 4-CH), 8.50 (s, CSNH₂).

3-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-propanone-1-thiosemicarbazone (10h) : A solution of the dibromoketone (**1h**; 0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) and thiosemicarbazide (0.04 mol) in glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 6 h. The solvent was then removed and the separated solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from methanol as orange needles (70%), m.p. 133–35° (Found : C, 60.90; H, 4.50; N, 13.39. C₁₆H₁₄N₃SCl requires : C, 60.95; H, 4.44; N, 13.31%); ν_{max} 3 472 (NH), 3 433 (NH₂), 1 589 (C=N), 1 546 (C=C), 1 256 (C=S), 770 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); λ_{max} (EtOH) (e) 2 366, 210 nm (3 155); δ 300 ((CD₃)₂SO) 9.00 (2H, s, thioamide), 8.30 (1H, s, imino), 7.50–8.60 (11H, m, 2-CH, 3-CH, ArH).

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